

TEACHING THE USE OF STUDENTS' INDEPENDENT WORK REFLECTION DURING PEDAGOGICAL PRACTICE IN THE ORGANIZATION

Erkayev Eldor Abdugarimovich

Fergana branch of UzDJTSU

eldorbekerkaev@gmail.ru

+998975978700

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Abstract Reflective practice is described as an active, dynamic, action-based skill set that develops in real time and in complex real-life situations. Reflection is a purposeful reflection on thoughts, feelings, and events related to a recent experience.

Keywords Reflection, thought, specific problems, self-awareness, self-reflection, personal self-development, thinking, reflection, thinking, emotional reaction.

Reflection can be defined as the process of thinking about one's actions, which allows students to stop and think about what is happening in their learning space. This study is a theoretical analysis of the existing conditions for the meaning and role of students' reflection in education. According to the results of the analysis, it is true that reflection is naturally possible to activate students' interaction with the educational material, deepen their understanding of the subject, and fostering independent thinking and thereby creating an effective learning environment. That work frames reflective practice as a combination of four key components: descriptive experience; analysis of experience; creating new meanings and concepts; behavior change efforts. Prospects for developing thinking through reflective journal writing are discussed, contributing to students' awareness of reflective writing as a tool for self-development.

Possible options for practical work with a reflective diary in learning science are offered.

Today, the development of the ability to learn independently is presented as an important problem facing education in the 21st century. However, this issue is understudied, and the academic literature rarely focuses on reflection, self-awareness, and student attitudes.

M.G. In Evdokimova's works, she emphasizes the traditional direction of education that technical rationality is not enough to solve complex problems. Technical rationality greatly contributes to the solution of professional problems by applying general theoretical principles applied to specific problems. Technical rationality greatly contributes to the solution of professional problems by applying general theoretical principles applied to specific problems. However, the standardization that results from this process does not teach participation in the "...spontaneous, intuitive functioning of everyday life."

This requires more complex development skills based on reflection and self-awareness. One of the first proponents of developing self-awareness in education was D. Dewey, who believed that reflection is any believes that belief is an active, persistent, and careful consideration of or assumed form of knowledge, the grounds that support it, and the subsequent conclusions to which it tends. D. Dewey calls reflection an active and intentional process that can begin with some discomfort during experience and end with learning and

deeper understanding. According to D. Dewey, aspects of reflective thinking include misunderstanding, analysis, hypothesis generation, hypothesis comparison, and action. They have more

D. Dewey's later works emphasize the positive role of reflection in the development of students' self-reflection, critical thinking, and professional values, meaning, and skills. Reflection and its contribution to the holistic development of students have attracted much attention from scholars and practitioners in recent years. Recognizing the importance of reflection in terms of empowering, motivating and empowering learners to take responsibility for their learning is undeniable.

Reflection naturally creates an effective learning environment that can stimulate further interaction with the learning material, deepen students' understanding of the subject matter, and enhance independent thinking.

In the works of OV. Berezhnova and EA Enns argue that modern education is necessary focusing on the development of reflection "... general education as one of the methods of personal self-development and modernization" VV Kulikov and IA Zayarna noted that reflection functions in a practical special way its implementation does not doubt its enormous value and should be organized. LN Osipova emphasizes the fact: "The teacher forms students' abilities to absorb and reflect on the material, increases the quality of the educational process "

Each of the aforementioned researchers called for a restructuring of education reflective principles that suggest that reflective practice can be developed in education. Thus, through internal communication, a "method" of self-awareness can emerge. Thus, reflection of personal experience and learning can be combined through the method of filling a diary that reflects the learning process, when students interact with the content of the subject, relationships and their own experiences. The purpose of this activity is to deepen students' understanding of their own experience and to develop thinking skills that actively involve them in the learning process.

Reflective practice is described as an active, dynamic, movement-based skill set that develops in real time and in complex real-life situations. Reflection is a purposeful reflection on thoughts, feelings, and events related to a recent experience. When examined carefully, one questions the established thinking and feelings based on one's direct experience. Through further reflection and experiential exploration, one creates and defines personal meaning. In the practice of thinking, four main components can be distinguished: description of experience; analysis experience; creating new meanings and concepts; behavior change efforts. The first component is experience, which serves as a context for learning. Direct thinking begins with formulating key questions that describe the experience. Based on this, the second component appears - mental activity that reviews and analyzes the experienced experience. These mental activities are structured around experiences that can cause emotional discomfort; the third formative component is the creation of new meanings and concepts. On the other hand, the weakening of emotional disturbance involves carefully looking at the experience, if a person is aware, should lead to constructive actions against existing attitudes and patterns. Thus, the fourth component of reflection appears - actions to change behavior. The process of thinking itself requires the process of awareness, which is how LN Osipova describes the quality of human behavior that connects thought and action in relation to oneself and others.

The quality of this relationship is maintained through the reflection of actions and represents the experience of the relationship between teacher and student in education. Thus, reflection is a state of mind as much as a set of actions, the ultimate process is not to solve the experience, but to better understand it. Thinking ultimately leads to action to change behavior by reflecting on one's experience. A reflective journal can be used in learning any subject. However, Experience shows that this method works most effectively in the study of the sciences of the humanitarian cycle related to the analysis of human behavior. The purpose of keeping a reflective diary

is to test students' awareness of their internal knowledge through three the main question: who am I? Why am I here? What is the purpose of my life? Thus, the purpose of the reflective diary is to help students become more mindful and aware of their daily activities.

A key element of reflective diaries is experienced personal thoughts. This is difficult for many readers because of the familiar passive understanding of academic writing and the unfamiliar act of using a personal understanding that is very different from the reference text. Also, reflective journaling requires more than personal thought: the challenge for readers is to open up in the writing process on a very personal level, which means being honest and authentic when they write. This content carries the risk of personal discovery, they wrote. When filling out a reflective diary, students are asked to invest more in a part of their personality in the writing that makes them sensitive to assessment. This fact makes it difficult to evaluate records

and makes it difficult to use a grade-reflective diary in teaching, because their subjective nature does not correspond to any quantitative criteria. In addition, when a reflective diary is assessed, the assessment becomes the focus and limits freedom of expression and creativity. On the other hand, assessment can encourage preparation and participation in classes, which can encourage a more careful approach to learning. Thus, there are conflicting opinions about the role of assessment and its impact on education. However, Evseeva L.N., Zhemchugova S.A., Safronenkova E.L. otmechayut ,Note that assessment is pedagogically important, as it strongly influences learning, and also sends signals about what the teacher considers important to reflect in the diary. To encourage learning, you should choose to keep a reflective diary option. The assessment work in any subject should be related to the reflective daily work in the author's opinion, consider the following components: then at least three reflective entries in the diary each lesson (20%), teaching at the end of the discipline final reflection report on (20%) - in addition, these two tasks are the focus of this article - the performance of didactic tasks in subjects (25%), reading and reviewing educational literature (25%) and attending classes (10%). As noted above, reflective journaling can be a powerful mechanism for developing students' thinking. In order to engage students in this practice, two parts of the assessment—reflective notes after each lesson and a final reflective note—are important.

According to the classical principles of didactics, evaluation criteria play a key role

Writing journals are successful because they provide a structure and foundation for what is expected of the student. It clarifies the goals and helps students to go beyond the prescribed description of their own experiences. In addition, clear instructions are given about the structure of the entry. The article explores the theoretical and methodological foundations and practical means of popularizing sports among students and youth, further

strengthening their physical activity and health, innovative factors for the formation of healthy lifestyle skills through the sports factor, the need to apply the advanced foreign experience in this regard to the education of physical education of our country.¹

This instruction is consistent with the above literature review, related to reflection as a method: describing experience, analyzing it, creating new meaning from experience, and actions to learn new behavior. . Each student should have access to a guide before the start of teaching reflective diary evaluation principles and criteria. The second part of completing the reflective diary is the final presentation of the most important thing in the students' learning activities after the course. This should be done after the academic discipline ends and thus allows for a deeper understanding of the learning process during the course. For this, there are three main questions, on which each student makes a reflective assessment.

1. Describe and analyze your learning path during the course
2. Give examples of how changes in thinking occurred during the lesson they happened
3. How do you apply the results of your thinking practice in your daily life and learning process?

Other questions should be asked that the students may ask more extensive analysis. Thus, writing reflective diaries requires students to develop the ability to express themselves in a new way, to find their own personal meaning. We can say that this process encourages them to connect first with your heart and then with your head. It shifts the emphasis from "I think..." to "I feel..." which creates an opportunity to refer to the inner meaning of self-learning. Thus, the use of personal opinion provides an opportunity to further explore one's own experience. An important task in writing reflective diaries is to encourage students to focus on one situation that they can analyze, rather than trying to cover the entire learning experience. To achieve this goal, you need to provide them with guidelines and criteria for completing the diary. For example, you could suggest the following writing structure:

1. Subject.
2. Description of an event/event/situation.
3. Emotional reaction.
4. Analysis (through personal reflection and subject matter).
5. Learning and changing your behavior

By asking the students to identify the topic, the teacher helps them to more clearly formulate the purpose of the reflective note. Describe an emotional feeling that students are more capable of by framing the event. And deep reflection is accompanied by a clear definition emotional reaction. Also, in the process of writing, students should be encouraged to connect their own academic knowledge with this analysis.

This article outlines the need for an integrated approach to teaching the harmonious generation. The article also describes how to integrate physical and spiritual-moral education in the personality of the student.²

The last stage of this method is learning and changing yourself, behavior that has already occurred at a deeper level of understanding. So reflective

¹ Egamberdieva, T. A., & Toshtemirov, O. A. (2020). Innovative-pedagogical features of the promotion of physical activity and culture of student-youth. *Fan-To-Sport*, (5), 56-59.

² Тоштемиров, О. А., & Аминжонов, А. А. (2019). Integration of physical and spiritual education social-pedagogical factors. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 1(9), 244-249.

Daily helps students develop self-awareness.

By understanding and using reasoning, one can also develop the ability to communicate with others. Current research in the field of reflection provides contemporary school teachers with an undeniable and solid basis for implementing reflective practices on a larger scale . One of the promising methods of organizing students' independent work is to use a diary that reflects the author's opinion in teaching. In addition, reflective journaling is associated with the development of personal qualities, such as purposefulness, interest in learning, critical self-evaluation, and systematic thinking. Now studying scientific heritage, socio-political activities and acquaintance youth charity of our above-stated ancestors is considered one of the main urgent objectives of the modern intellectuals.³

Summary: This article discusses the use of a reflective diary as a method of developing reflection in the educational process. The results of this approach to education allow for reflective practice in everyday activities. The role of critical thinking reflection in development is revealed. As indicated, reflective journaling is an important exercise, reports that can require as much time and effort from students as traditional essays. The present study shows assessment as a potential tool to enable students to use the reflective diary method more effectively.

³ Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). Eastern Renaissance And Its Cultural Heritage: The View Of Foreign Researchers. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(05), 211-215.

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